

Emerging Trends of Green Marketing in India

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& Rajadurai, N.

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Dr.K.Srinivasan., M.Com.,M.Phil.,Ph.D.,

Vice Principal and Assistant Professor in Commerce

PG & Research Department of Commerce

Morappur Kongu College of Arts and Science, Morappur, Dharmapuri (Dt)

N.Rajadurai

M.Phil. (Research Scholar-PG & Research Department of Commerce)

Morappur Kongu College of Arts and Science, Morappur

Abstract

The natural way of living whole enhances the eco-friendly in that nature. We have to upkeep the natural as it provides everyone we processing in the earth. In the modern era of globalization, it is become challenging to keep the customers as well as consumers in the fold and even keep our natural environment safe and that is the biggest need of the time. Environment pollution is buzzwords in today of on safe business environment. The customer is also aware of the environment issue like global warming, etc.. Recently the climate change issue has come to the forefront. Climate change is global warming. It is the threat to social and economic stable and sustainable human essence. There is no doubt that climate change affects the fundamental requirement for health – clean air, safe drinking of water, sufficient green food and secured level of the environment. The paper described the current Centro of the Indian market and explored the challenge and opportunities business have with the green market, why companies are adopting it and future of green marketing and conclusions that green marketing is summing that will continuous grow in both put into practice and insist.

Keywords: Green product, Climate change, Corporate Social Responsibility, Environment pollution.

Introduction

Today consumer is becoming more and more conscious about the environment and is also becoming socially responsible. Therefore, more companies are responsible for consumer's aspirers for environmentally fewer damages or natural product. Green marketing promotes the environmental benefit of product or companies are increase integrate they're that environmental value into their purchasing that nature. More and more customer want into the support that companies that incorporate sustainably efforts their products and service.

There are many environmental issues impacted by the production of goods and services and the rendering of services, and there are also many

Dynamics of audience consumer behavior is very complex as well as the fascinating area for the researchers and marketers. Rural audience behavior is an interesting and significance study to make the marketing process effective. The rural audience is different from the urban audience regarding receiving the messages from television advertising and reacting to the same. Increased investment in the rural market by marketers has enhanced the purchasing power of the rural buyers. This has caused curiosity for many marketers to focus on rural customers and to understand their response to television advertisements.

Green marketing products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. It incorporates a broad range of activities, including product modification, changes to well as modifying advertising. Defining green marketing is not a simple task where several meanings intersect and contradict each other; an example of this will be the existence of varying social, environmental and retail definitions attached to this term. Other similar terms used are environmental marketing and ecological marketing.

Green, environmental and eco-marketing is part of the new marketing approaches which do not just refocus, adjust or enhance existing marketing thinking and practice, but seek to challenge those approaches and provide a substantially different perspective. In more detail green, environmental and eco-marketing belong to the group of approaches which seek to address the lack of fit between marketing as it is currently practiced and the ecological and social realities of the wider marketing environment.

Green marketing is a practice whereby companies seek to go above and beyond traditional marketing by promoting environmental core values in the hope that consumers will associate these values with their company or brand. Engaging in these sustainable activities can lead to creating a new Product line that caters to the new target market. This is also sometimes known as sustainable marketing, environmental marketing or ecological marketing.

Ben and Jerry's, Whole Foods, Starbucks, Johnson & Johnson, Method and Timberland are among the publicly traded companies that have employed green marketing strategies, stressing the sustainability of their products or the green methods employed in their packaging or retail stores.

Green marketing may refer to the production process, to the products or services themselves, or both. Companies that succeed in "going green" can attract the attention and investment dollars of those pursuing socially responsible investments an investment strategy of owning shares of only those companies that have committed to sustainability, social responsibility and good corporate governance. Once a niche market, SRI investing has grown rapidly in the past few years, with several SRI mutual funds and ETFs offered that actively look for companies such as those with green marketing practices.

Are Consumers Willing to Pay More for Green Marketing?

Green marketing and ESG practices come with added costs that are often passed on to the consumer. This is because more expensive materials, such as recycled products, are used; because waste must be reduced; and because often these products must compete with non-green alternatives, to name a few. The 2014 Nielsen Global Survey on Corporate Social Responsibility asked 30,000 consumers from 60 countries to explain their preferences for green products. They found that a majority of consumers are indeed willing to pay for green marketing. Some 55% of consumers were willing to pay extra for products and services from companies committed to positive social and environmental impact (up from 45% in 2011), and 52% had made at least one purchase in the previous six months from at least one socially responsible company. More than half of respondents reported checking product packaging to make sure it was not wasteful or harmful to the environment. Consumers in the Asia-Pacific region, Latin America and the Middle East/Africa showed a higher preference (64%, 63%, 63%) to pay extra for green, while in North America and Europe preferences were a bit lower.

Corporate Social Responsibility

The corporate social responsibility is a type of international private business self-regulation. [2] While once it was possible to describe CSR as an internal organizational policy or corporate social ethical that time has passed as various international laws have been developed and various organizations have used their authority to push it beyond individual or even industry-wide initiatives. While it has been considered a form of corporate legal vale for some time, over the last decade or so it has moved considerably from voluntary decisions at the level of individual organizations, to mandatory schemes at regional, national and even transnational levels.

Considered at the organizational level, CSR is an organizational policy. As such, it must align with and be integrated into a business mode to be successful. With some models, a firm's implementation of CSR goes beyond compliance with regulatory requirements, and engages in "actions that appear to further some social good, beyond the interests of the firm and that which is required by law" The choices of 'complying' with the law, failing to comply, and 'going beyond' are three distinct strategic organizational choices. While in many areas such as environmental or labor regulations, employers may choose to comply with the law or go beyond the law, other organizations may choose to flout the law. These organizations are taking on clear legal risks. The nature of the legal risk, however, changes when attention is paid to the Soft law may incurred legal liability particularly when businesses make misleading claims about their sustainability or other ethical credentials and practices. Overall, businesses may engage in CSR for strategic or ethical purposes. From a strategic perspective, the aim is to increase long-term profits and shareholder trust through positive public relations and high ethical standards to reduce business and legal risk by taking responsibility for corporate actions. CSR strategies encourage the company to make a positive impact on the environment and state holders including consumers, employees, investors, communities, and others. From an ethical perspective, some businesses will adopt CSR policies and practices because of ethical beliefs of senior management. For example, a CEO may believe that harming the environment is ethically objectionable.

Proponents argue that corporation increases long-term profits by operating with a CSR perspective, while critics argue that CSR distracts from businesses' economic role. A 2000 study compared existing economic studies of the relationship between social and financial performance, concluding that the contradictory results of previous studies reporting positive, negative, and neutral financial impact, were due to flawed metrical analysis and claimed when the study is properly specified, CSR has a neutral impact on financial outcomes. Critics questioned the "lofty" and sometimes "unrealistic expectations" in CSR.[13] or that CSR is merely or an attempt to pre-empt the role of governments as a watchdog over powerful multinational corporation In line with this critical perspective, political.

Sociological became interested in CSR in the context of theories of Some institutionalizes viewed CSR as a form of capitalist legitimacy and in particular point out that what began as a social movement against uninhibited was transformed by corporations into a 'business model' and a 'risk management' device, often with questionable results.

CSR is titled to aid an organization's mission as well as serve as a guide to what the company represents for its consumers. Business power is the part of applied ethics that examines ethical principles and moral or ethical problems that can arise in a business environment. The recognized international standard for CSR. Public sector organizations (the United Nations for example) adhere to is widely accepted that CSR adheres to similar principles, but with no formal act of legislation.

Government Polices of Green Economic

The green economy is defined as an economic that aims at reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities, and that aims for suitability of development without environment. It is closely related with the ecological environment but has a more politically applied focus. The 2011 UNPA

Green Economy Report argues “that to be green; an economy must not only be efficient but also fair. Fairness implies recognizing global and country level equity dimensions, particularly in assuring a just transition to an economy that is low-carbon, resource efficient, and socially inclusive.

Green Sticker and eco-label practices have emerged as consumer-facing measurements of friendliness to the environment and sustainable development. Many industries are starting to adopt these standards as a viable way to promote their greening practices in a globalized economy.

“Green economics” is loosely defined as any theory of economics by which an economy is considered to be component of the ecosystem in which it resides. A holistic approach to the subject is typical, such that economic ideas are commingled with any number of other subjects, depending on the particular theorist.

The use of the term is further ambiguities by the political distinction of green practices which are formally organized and claim the capital-G “Green” term as a unique and distinguishing mark. It is thus preferable to refer to a loose school of “green economists” who generally advocate shifts towards a green and a fuller accounting for biodiversity.

Some economists view green economics as a branch or subfield of more established schools. For instance, it is regarded as the classical value where the traditional land is generalized to natural capital and has some attributes in common with labor and physical capital (since natural capital assets like rivers directly substitute for man-made ones such as Indian economic). Or, it is viewed as mixed economic with nature represented as a form ecological system, an exploited base of non-human workers providing surplus value to the human economy, or as a branch of ecological in which the price of life for developing vs. developed nations is held steady at a ratio reflecting a balance of power and that of non-human life is very low. An increasing commitment by the UNEP (and national governments such as the UK) to the ideas of natural capital and full cost accounting under the banner ‘green economy’ could blur distinctions between the schools and redefine them all as variations of “green economics.” Institutions (notably the world bank and International monetary fund (via its “Green Fund” initiative) responsible for global monetary policy have stated a clear intention to move towards valuation and a more official and universal biodiversity Taking these into account targeting not less but radically zero emission and waste is what is promoted by the green analysis of economic. The UNEP 2011 Green Economy Report informs that “based on existing studies, the annual financing demand to green the global economy was estimated to be in the range US\$ 1.05 to US\$ 2.59 trillion. To place this demand in perspective, it is about one-tenth of total global investment per year, as measured by global Gross Capital Formation.

Conclusion

The green marketing concept is covered in more than one valuable level of on environmental protection of the company. While the firm is using to that more than that social reasonability for that environmental detractor of that consumer’s value of that particular value of that product. The pollution of that environment because much of their package finishing up as reasonable waste. It must be redeemable that the using of various level of these particular valuable goods. Every organization mostly knows that the social protection reasonability of on everyone.

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